

SOME ASPECTS OF THE USE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES TO IMPROVE STUDENTS' CREATIVITY IN HISTORY CLASSES

Usmonaliyeva Risolat Umaraliyevna

Senior teacher of the department “Methodology of Socio-Economic Sciences” of the
Surkhandarya Region National Center for Training Pedagogies in New Methodologies

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Abstract. *A new approach to history lessons. Ways to increase students' creativity in history lessons. Some aspects of improving students' creativity in history lessons. Problem-based learning in the development of students' creativity in history classes. Use of pedagogical technologies to improve students' creativity in history lessons. Use of interactive methods to improve students' creativity in history classes.*

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Our age is the age of technology. Organization of classes based on new, modern approaches is the need of the hour. It is important to improve the thinking of young students. Problem-based education and the use of modern, advanced pedagogical technologies are of great importance in expanding students' worldview, developing thinking skills. When we think about problem-based learning, immediate questions arise. What is this education, what are its theoretical foundations? How does it differ from traditional education? What is the purpose of problem-based learning?

In the course and extracurricular activities, students can expand their thinking circles, form independent reading and learning skills, encourage active action, work in cooperation, develop their speech, as well as use advanced pedagogical technologies in the lesson to make students able to speak and justify their opinions based on evidence and grounds. It is to avoid generalizations and to teach always to speak through arguments and facts. I think it is appropriate to pay attention to the aspects of problem-based teaching in history classes to increase students' creativity.

Problem-based education is an advanced result of continuous research and experiments carried out by pedagogues in the 70s and 80s of the 20th century. Problem-based education is the effective resolution of two ideas in the teacher's activity, that is, what part of knowledge to give to the student, and how to give it. Problem-based learning is a cooperative activity of the teacher and students at the same time in the lesson. The level of activity of the teacher in mastering the complex part of the content learned in the lesson is to bring the activity of students to the same level. Problem-based learning is mainly focused on students' free thinking and expression of this thought, and it is to influence its further development. Problem-based education develops important characteristics of the student's personality, creative thinking skills. For this, the teacher focuses the students' thinking in different directions, relying on ready and additional knowledge, namely:

- a) listen carefully;
- b) independent, solitary thinking;
- c) thinking as a team;
- g) analysis;
- d) discussion as a majority;
- e) perform relevant logical tasks, etc.

The purpose of the above directions is to activate the actions of students in every way. So, if the students actively listen to the teacher's assignment, analyze it and make a clear opinion, and accordingly do some kind of practical work, it can be considered that the educational process was actively conducted.

At the same time, if the teacher uses the narrative method in learning a new topic, makes the narrative effective, and makes effective use of exhibitions, and at the end of the narrative, practical work is carried out with some students, it can be considered that the educational process has become active, learning has been effective.

It is worth saying that in the above two cases, the activity of the students is directed in different directions by the teacher.

Problem-based education requires the teacher to act clearly, allocate time correctly, and understand the effect of training in advance. One of the important conditions for solving this problem is the preparation of the teacher for the upcoming training session. In preparation, it is necessary to take into account all aspects of problem-based education, determine the appropriate form for the subject, and develop its method. Only then, the training will make it possible to fulfill the following requirements given in the State Education Standard.

1. The ability of students to express their independent opinion or reaction to the process and events taking place in the countries of the world or in some societies.
2. Acquire relevant knowledge through independent study of historical sources.
3. Analysis, comparison and proof of acquired knowledge, conclusions.
4. As a result of thorough assimilation of scientific knowledge, they come to a certain educational conclusion, etc.

There are a number of difficulties in choosing and applying one of the known forms of problem-based learning. These difficulties are manifested even in experienced teachers, which are formed depending on the level of professional skills of the teacher.

There are basically four challenges in preparing for problem-based learning.

The first difficulty is seen in the formulation of the selected problems and the method of problem study. This method should not only ensure mastery of educational material, but also ensure students' independence in cognitive activities. The solution to this difficulty is seen in the feedback from the students and the correctness of this response.

The second challenge appears to be defining what problem-based learning looks like and applying it to all or some groups of students in the classroom. This difficulty arises from the teacher's lack of understanding of the problem situation and problem statement.

The third challenge is seen in the teacher's problematization of new concepts, their categorization, distribution and implementation by students. Because, when solving the given problem, each student interprets it in his own way.

The fourth difficulty is seen in the teacher's ability to arouse students' interest in the lesson and continuously develop it. Because, the teacher may lack experience in regularly focusing the student's attention on one point.

A problem situation can be formed in all educational activities. How much to shape it depends on the teacher. The importance of the problem situation is that it focuses the attention of the students on one point, that is, the problem. This increases the effectiveness of the statement and has a positive effect on the quality of learning by organizing the students' research to a certain extent. The problem situation can be formed anywhere in the content, starting with the outline of

the subject to be studied. When the teacher gives the topic and its plan to the students, it is appropriate to tell them which parts of the plan are complicated and what they need to pay attention to at this point.

A problem statement is different from a simple statement. Although students are interested in this historical event in a simple narrative, their intellectual research is not formed in relation to this knowledge. Because historical processes or events are presented or studied in the same way as they are presented in the textbook.

The advantage of problem statement is that after the statement, the teacher tells the students what they need to think about themselves. However, in an essay, the teacher systematically presents evidence or ideas that help them identify and articulate those ideas.

It is necessary that the scientific evidence presented by the teacher in the report should be clear and consistent with the content. The teacher's professional skills are also important in the description. The ability of the teacher to attract all students to the existing problem with the fluency and effectiveness of his speech leads to the expected result. Therefore, it can be considered that the teacher's skills are effective. A problem statement influences students' creative explorations and cognitive abilities. The extent to which this idea has been resolved will become more apparent when further responses are received from students.

From the conducted experiments, it became clear that it is impossible to conduct topics related to history and law in the method of a complete problem statement. If this is done, the teacher loses time. It is recommended to use the problem statement only in the relevant areas of the content, that is, in the complex areas of the content, on the content that the students need to master. So, the student will have to decide in which part of the subject content to use the problem statement method during the preparation for the lesson.

Logical work is practical work and its result on the way to solve the problem set before the students by the teacher. The main purpose of logical works is to ensure the planned mastery of students by strengthening their intellectual research, to achieve their long-term memory, and to form several skills and competencies in students.

There are many complex topics in upper grades or academic lyceums and vocational colleges. In particular, the volume of topics related to the XIX-XX centuries of world history is large, and there are many complex concepts in them. The teacher's training can achieve the students' mastery at a minimum level with the problem statement, problem situation and relevant questions during the training sessions on those topics. Making the mastered knowledge whole, raising its scientific level to the required level, drawing students' clear conclusions about this knowledge, as well as historical processes create a problematic statement or situation, the possibility of formation of their confidence, in some cases, logical works seem to be important and give their proof.

For this purpose, when choosing logical tasks, the teacher should first of all take into account the importance of mastering the complex part of the studied subject, pay attention to the size of the logical task and calculate in advance the time spent on it, whether the material is sufficient, and the ability of the students to perform the logical task. Otherwise, it is difficult to achieve the goal.

Modern pedagogical technology is new methods of various forms that have entered the educational process, and its content is aimed at the activation of student activity. In terms of its

purpose and essence, it is to form the cooperation of teachers and students in the educational process, to actively acquire historical knowledge and to direct them to actively demonstrate it.

The actions taken by the teacher in order to increase the activity of the students in finding solutions to the problems, drawing conclusions and putting the actions on the shoulders of more students when the time comes, represent the content of the new pedagogical technology, and the finding of effective ways of mastering it expresses its purpose.

Pedagogical technology entered the educational process in such forms as "Brainstorming", "Critical thinking", "Have your point of view", "Debates", "Everyone teaches everyone", "Working in small groups", "Insert", "Cluster", and now their number approached 100 per day. However, regardless of their forms and methods, the goal is to increase the activity of students, ensure the thorough assimilation of historical knowledge and the formation of relevant skills.

The goal of problem-based education is to equalize the activity of students with the activity of the teacher, to form their cooperation with each other. In order to make our thoughts more understandable to the readers, it is necessary to analyze some aspects of pedagogical technology from the point of view of problem-based education.

Educational technologies aimed at increasing the creativity of young students form the basis of lessons held in each subject and activities organized outside the classroom in general secondary schools.

From the implementation of all methods of modern pedagogical technology, it was concluded that problem-based education is the methodological basis of pedagogical technology. If we assume that problem-based learning is a tree, problem situation, problem statement, and logic work are its major branches. Modern pedagogical technology is a new branch of these three. They cannot be separated from each other. Problem-based learning also has advantages over new pedagogical technology. That is, in problem-based education, attention is paid to the live speech of the teacher. In the process of learning a new topic or after learning it, the live speech of the teacher increases the educational value of the content and improves the quality of learning. In the new pedagogical technology methods, there are no ideas about the live speech of the teacher.

In conclusion, for the effective use of modern pedagogical technology, first of all, it is necessary to have the skills of learning, mastering and applying problem-based education.

If problem-based education is combined with new pedagogical technology, the content of education will be deepened, educational quality will increase, that is, the requirements of the State Education Standard will be met.

REFERENCES

1. Mirziyoev Sh.M. "We will resolutely continue our path of national development and raise it to a new level." T., 2017.
2. Akhmedov V. "Lessons from History", T., "Teacher", 1994.
3. New history of Uzbekistan. Uzbekistan in the years of independence. Book 3. East. T., 2000.
4. National encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. t.1-2.-T., UzMU publishing house, 2000-2001.
5. Azizkhodjaeva N.N. Pedagogical technology and pedagogical skill - T., 2006.
6. Achilov M. "New pedagogical technologies" / manual. - against: Nasaf, 2000.
7. Farberman B. Advanced pedagogical technologies - T., 2001.
8. Tolipov O'.K., Usmonboeva M.. Structural basis of pedagogical technologies - T., 2006.

9. Yoldoshev J.G., Usmanov S.A. Fundamentals of pedagogical technology. -T: "Teacher", 2004.
10. Yoldoshev J.G'. Education is on the way to renewal. - T.: "Teacher". 2000.